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Research Article

**STUDY OF MOTHERS' PSYCHOLOGICAL CONDITION IN
THE POSTPARTUM PERIOD**¹Ayesha Rashid, ²Iram Javed, ³Muhammad Waleed Ghani
^{1,2,3}The University Of Lahore, Lahore.**Article Received:** November 2020 **Accepted:** December 2020 **Published:** January 2021**Abstract:****Objective:** This study aims to explore mental and psychological functioning in mothers during their postpartum time.**Setting and Design:** The design of the study was cross-sectional observational. This study was held in the University Of Lahore Teaching Hospital, Lahore over a three month period from July 2020 to september 2020 .**Subject and Method:** 70 women were included in this study during their postpartum period. The technique of systematic random sampling has been adopted. The data were analyzed in version 20 of SPSS.**Conclusions:** For the peace and prosperity of society as a whole, an environment conducive to the mother's personal development and child development is necessary. Therefore, as a nation, we have to pay attention to the mother's mental health both during pregnancy and after childbirth through special counselling for parents.**Keywords:** postpartum period, Mothers' psychological state.**Corresponding author:****Ayesha Rashid,**
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INTRODUCTION:

A child's birth is a life event full of excitement, anticipation and joy. The transition and adaptation to new requirements, roles and responsibilities can, however, be stressful. The mother's mental changes during the postpartum period are of great importance since mood changes affect the infant directly. New mothers undergo many psychological and physiological changes after a child is born. Depression, anxiety, and insomnia are the most common psychological problems in new mothers during the postpartum period. Research has shown that social support is an essential buffer for postpartum depression. However, little is known about the perceptions of women about social support in the postpartum period. The postpartum period is the time of the risk of maternal postpartum depression. The general maternal results of maternal postpartum depression are not systematically assessed.

Objective:

This study aims to explore the mental and psychological functioning of mothers during their postpartum period.

Setting and Design:

The design of the study was cross-sectional observational.

SUBJECTS AND METHODS:

70 women were included in this study in their postpartum period. The technique of systematic random sampling has been adopted. Some people had changed their mind, and some refused to participate, due to difficulties in reaching and recruiting women in urban areas. The majority of women who participated in this study came from rural areas. A sample of women was taken from 32 to 42 weeks of pregnancy until 12 weeks after pregnancy.

Statistical Analysis:

The data were analyzed in version 20 of SPSS. Data were analyzed with version 20 of SPSS. The mean and standard deviations (SD) and the categorical variables are presented as numbers and percentages.

RESULTS:

The results showed that most women in the postpartum period felt refreshed and energetic. Only 1.4% of women felt uncooled at all. However, 54.4% of women felt mild to moderate, and 44.3% felt incredibly refreshed. In terms of energy, 12.9% of the mother did not feel energetic at all, 74.3% had comparatively low levels of energy and 12.9% extremely energetic. The study found that 84.3% had

no depression, 12.9% had mild to moderate depression, but 2.9% had shallow depressions. Similarly, 80% of the mothers were not tensed, but 19.9% of them suffered a mild to moderate degree of mental change. When asked about tiredness, 45.7% of women were unable to be tired, 51.5% were moderately tired, and 2.9% extremely tired. 81.4% of mothers did not have concentration problems, 15.7% had moderate changes in concentration level, and 2.9% had severe problems.

CONCLUSION:

An environment conducive to the mother's personal development and child development is necessary for social peace and prosperity as a whole. Therefore, as a nation, we have to pay attention to the mother's mental health both during pregnancy and after childbirth through special counselling for parents. Further research is recommended to study whether our findings can be replicated or whether different association patterns emerge. Larger sample size and more rigorous research design are critical for future research. The results highlight the need for mental health screening and a broader approach to thinking in this population about maternal stress and psychological distress. Based on the participants' positive comments on the non-pharmacological, non-invasive and self-management aspects of the proposed intervention, the mothers in our study wanted to use a CES to treat depression, anxiety and insomnia or to prevent them from occurring. The research study results support the collection of feasible and acceptable data and outcome measures for the study of psychological distress in new mothers during the postpartum period.

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